

Electronic interaction between metal centres in binuclear complexes with long bridges[†]

Pabitra K. Bhattacharya

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, M. S. University of Baroda, Vadodara-390 002, India

The biochemical systems involve organic molecules with potential coordinating sites, and strongly coordinating transition metal ions, hence, there is abundance of metal complexes in the biological systems. Since the biomolecules have more than one coordinating site, the complexes in biological system are bi- and polynuclear in character. Bimetallic centres are considered to be active sites in biomolecules like Cu^{II} proteins, oxidases (with type I, type II and binuclear type III copper(II) centres), diphenol oxidase, tyrosinase and hemo-cyanin, homo-binuclear Fe^{III} proteins like hemerythrin and hetero-binuclear sites like superoxide dismutase (Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}) and cytochrome C oxidase (Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}). Study of binuclear complexes is also important from the point of view of some pathological conditions, under which for some unusual reasons, there is excess of metal ions in the bio-fluids.

Further, there is awareness of the importance of binuclear complexes of paramagnetic ions as models for industrial magnetic materials and catalysts. Hence, the study of the thermodynamic properties of the formation of the binuclear complexes in solution, electronic interaction between the two paramagnetic centres, and its consequences on the electrochemical and catalytic properties of the binuclear complexes has attracted the attention of the chemists. The present paper deals with the study of the above properties of some binuclear Cu^{II} and Ru^{III} complexes.

Thermodynamic study of the formation of binuclear complexes

Histidine is an important ligand involved in Cu^{II} exchange in biochemical reactions. It is an ambidentate ligand with two probable coordination sites¹ (Fig. 1): (i) involving glycine like coordination at low pH (1.8–3.2) [CuHHist]²⁺ with imidazole nitrogen remaining protonated, and (ii) histamine like coordination at high pH, with coordination from nitrogen and imidazole nitrogen [CuHist]⁺, with possibility of weak coordination from carboxylate also.

The formation of such complexes has been confirmed by electronic spectral and electrochemical studies².

Fig. 1

In case of excess of Cu^{II} ion, histidine can coordinate to two Cu^{II} and forms a binuclear complex. In the binuclear complex, one Cu^{II} is bound to the histamine like site and another is bound at the monodentate carboxylate site³ (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2

$$\begin{array}{llll} \log K_{\text{Cu-OOCCH}_3}^{\text{Cu}} & \log K_{\text{CuHHist}}^{\text{Cu}} & \log K_{\text{CuHist}}^{\text{Cu}} & \log K_{\text{CuHistCu}}^{\text{Cu}} \\ 2.10 & 8.11 & 10.50 & 12.67 \\ \log K_{\text{CuHistCu}}^{\text{Cu}} = \log K_{\text{CuHist}}^{\text{Cu}} + \log K_{\text{Cu-OOCCH}_3}^{\text{Cu}} \end{array}$$

The value of $\log K_{\text{CuHistCu}}^{\text{Cu}}$ is comparable with the summation of $\log K_{\text{CuHist}}^{\text{Cu}}$ and $\log K_{\text{Cu-OOCCH}_3}^{\text{Cu}}$. This shows that the two coordinating sites of histidine bind independently with two Cu^{II} ions. There is no significant interaction between the two centres.

Another ambidentate ligand of biochemical importance is L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine (L-dopa), which acts as a neurotransmitter. In Cu^{II}-L-dopa system, in the pH range less than 5, there is amino acid coordination [CuLH₂] and in the pH range 5–7, there is pyrocatechol coordination [CuL]⁴ (Fig. 3).

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Fig. 3

It is interesting to observe that in a 2 : 1 mixture of Cu^{II} and L-dopa, there is formation of CuLH_2 at low pH (<3.8) and of binuclear complex at higher pH (~4.8) with one Cu^{II} bound to the amino acid site and another at catechol site⁵ (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4

$$\log K_{\text{CuLH}_2}^{\text{Cu}} \quad \log K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}} \quad \log K_{\text{CuL}_2\text{Cu}}^{\text{Cu}} \quad \log K_{\text{CuL}_2\text{Cu}}^{\text{CuLH}_2}$$

7.43 13.66 22.73 15.30

It is observed that the formation constant of CuLH_2 complex in 2 : 1 mixture of Cu^{II} and L-dopa is comparable to Cu-amino acid coordination as in 1 : 1 mixture. However, the constant for the binding of the second Cu^{II} with $\text{O}^- \text{O}^-$ site of L-dopa forming binuclear complex CuL_2Cu ($\log K_{\text{CuL}_2\text{Cu}}^{\text{CuLH}_2} = \log K_{\text{CuL}_2\text{Cu}}^{\text{Cu}} - \log K_{\text{CuLH}_2}^{\text{Cu}} = 15.30$) is higher than the constant for Cu^{II} binding to the catechol site of L-dopa ($\log K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}} = 13.66$). This indicates that the binding of Cu^{II} at amino acid end affects the binding tendency of the catecholate end, i.e. the electronic effect is communicated through the whole molecule and alludes to the possibility of interaction between the two metal centres in a binuclear complex, through the ligand bridge.

Electron spin coupling between two paramagnetic centres

In biological systems like type III Cu^{II} sites in oxidases, tyrosinase and oxyhemocyanin with peroxo bridge, the interaction between two paramagnetic centres leads to antiferromagnetism⁶. In such systems the interaction is not direct between the two metal centres, but is mediated through the orbitals of the intermediate bridging O_2^{2-} and is called super-exchange (Fig. 5).

The model systems are represented by binuclear complexes with exo-alkoxo, or endo-phenoxo bridges⁷⁻⁹ with bridging O^- (Figs. 6-8).

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

Fig. 8

The super exchange takes place through the σ -overlap of magnetic $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbitals of the two Cu^{II} centres with the p_x orbital of the bridging oxide. This results in a symmetric or antisymmetric interaction (Fig. 9). The separation of the energies of the two types of combinations is $2J$, where J is the spin exchange interaction constant¹⁰.

Fig. 9

When the separation between the bonding and the antibonding orbital, $2J > kT$, all the molecules are in the singlet ground state, resulting in diamagnetism. In cases where $2J \approx kT$, the paramagnetism is lower than expected,

depending on the Boltzman's population of states and leads to paramagnetism.

In a binuclear complex, the exchange interaction between the two Cu^{II} centres is possible, only if the molecule has a planar structure. This depends on the dihedral angle θ between the coordination planes of the two Cu^{II} centres and also the degree of planarity of the bridging unit, indicated by the angle $\tau^{10,11}$. If the bridging atom has trigonal planar sp^2 geometry, the entire unit Cu_2L approaches flat structure ($T = 0$). Further, if the coordination planes of the Cu^{II} are very approximately coplanar ($\theta = 0$), there is good overlap between the metal orbitals and the bridging orbitals and the magnetic coupling is quite strong.

As the geometry of the bridging atom approaches tetrahedral (sp^3 hybridization), there is distortion in the planarity, resulting in reduction in overlap of Cu^{II} $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbitals and the oxygen p_x orbital, and antiferromagnetic interaction is weakened. Thus in such cases the two metal centres may be constrained to have parallel spins, leading to ferromagnetism. Besides the above accidental case, ferromagnetism may also be due to strict orthogonality of the orbitals¹², e.g. in the heterodinuclear complex of Cu^{II} and Cr^{III} , the metal ions have unpaired electrons in orthogonal orbitals, $d_{x^2-y^2}$ in Cu^{II} and d_{z^2} in Cr^{III} , leading to ferromagnetism.

Another factor determining spin-exchange interaction in binuclear complexes is in-plane M-L-M angle ϕ^{13} . It has been observed that in the μ -hydroxo binuclear Cu^{II} complexes, there is a linear relationship between J and Cu-O-Cu angle ϕ . As the angle is reduced, crossing of the singlet and triplet takes place at $\phi \approx 97.6^\circ$.

In the complexes with two bridging ligands, the interaction through two dissimilar bridges may be complementary or non-complementary depending on the Hoffman's theory¹⁴, whether both bridging atoms interact with the same combination of the magnetic orbital or the bridging groups interact with different combinations of magnetic orbitals. In the case of μ -alkoxo- μ -acetato binuclear¹⁵, the p_x orbital of the bridging O^- interacts with the σ_a combination of the metal orbital to raise its energy, whereas the bridging acetate orbital interacts with the σ_s combination of the metal orbitals, thus raising its energy. Thus the energy separation between σ_s and σ_a decreases, resulting in decreased antiferromagnetic interaction.

The magnetic character is a combination of the extent of ferromagnetic and antiferromagnetic interaction through the two bridges¹⁶,

$$J = J_F + J_{AF}$$

For example, in μ -alkoxo- μ -azido dicopper complex, orbital complementary effect is operative, whereas in μ -alkoxo- μ -carboxylato dicopper complex there is anti-complementary effect.

Besides the spin exchange interaction in binuclear complexes through single atom bridges, long range spin cou-

pling may take place through multi-atom bridges. Such interaction is of significance to understand the mechanism of electron transfer between metal centres, separated by large organic molecules.

In case of structurally related binucleating ligands, acting as bridges (Fig. 10), the order of antiferromagnetic coupling has been observed to be oxalate < oxamate < oxamidato¹⁷.

Fig. 10

In oxalate and analogous ligand bridges, it has been shown, that the antiferromagnetic interaction is through σ -pathway. It depends on the following features : (i) nature and magnitude of overlap between the symmetry adapted linear combination of the metal atom orbitals and the four lone pair orbitals of the ligand, (ii) in-plane field created by the bridging ligand donor atoms, (iii) electronegativity of the ligand donor atom. Lesser the electronegativity, greater is the electron density on the two metal centres and hence higher the delocalization of the electrons on them and consequently, greater is the spin coupling.

The order of increasing antiferromagnetic coupling, on passing from oxalate to oxamide, can be explained on the basis of increase in the in-plane ligand field. In the complexes of the type L-Cu-X-Cu-L, the extent of spin coupling is dependent on the nature of the capping ligand L. It controls the energy of the metal orbital, thus reducing the difference in energies of the metal orbital and the bridging ligand orbital, resulting in higher orbital overlap and greater spin coupling. Kahn¹⁸ could tune the magnetic interaction in L-Cu-C₂O₄-Cu-L by using different capping ligands L.

The distance between the two metal centres has lesser effect on the antiferromagnetic interaction, than the matching of the symmetry and energy of the metal and the bridging atom orbitals. This is illustrated by the observation in the binuclear Ni^{II} complexes, with bridged dihydroxybenzoquinone or squarate¹⁹ (Fig. 11). Though the former is large, it affects more spin exchange interaction between the two Ni^{II} centres, because due to greater π -delocalization in squarate, there is lowering in energy of its bridging atom orbitals, hence, they have less matching with the metal orbitals, leading to less antiferromagnetic interaction.

Fig. 11

However, in the cases of binuclear complexes, where other factors in bridging ligands are comparable, the antiferromagnetic interaction decreases with increasing distance. For example, in the two complexes²⁰ presented in Fig. 12. The antiferromagnetic interaction is much more in I than in II with Cu-Cu separation of 12 Å.

The super exchange pathway in binuclear complexes may be through σ or π pathway of the bridging ligand.

Quantum mechanical calculations show²¹ that in naphthazarin bridged binuclear Cu^{II} complexes (Fig. 13), spin exchange interaction is propagated through π -electron system of the bridging ligand. The energies and the characteristics of the σ -molecular orbitals do not allow the interaction with the metal d -orbitals and hence could not be the possible path way for magnetic exchange interactions.

However, according to Hendrickson, in *p*-phenylenediamine, 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl or pyrazine bridged binuclear complexes (Fig. 14), the spin coupling interaction is through the highest occupied σ -molecular orbital of the bridging ligand²², which are symmetric combination of the N-lone-pair orbitals with minor contributions from p_z of the carbon atoms of the ring.

The fact that there is contribution from the π -orbitals of the bridging ligand, in the super-exchange, is supplemented by the observation²³ that in the binuclear complexes depicted in Fig. 15.

Fig. 15

The exchange interaction is less in the case of *m*-phenylenediamine based Schiff base complex than in *p*- or *o*-phenylenediamine based Schiff base complexes. This is because electronic interaction through π -bonds is minimum at *meta*-position.

However, molecular orbital analysis reveals that even in complexes with complete π -delocalization, super-exchange interaction predominantly involves the σ -orbitals of the aromatic bridging ligand. For example, in the following complex depicted in Fig. 16, though the π -delocalization is interrupted by the CH₂ group, spin-exchange interaction is observed²⁴.

Fig. 16

It has now been observed that the spin exchange interaction takes place in the binuclear complexes presented in Fig. 17, with bridges having no π -delocalization²⁵⁻²⁸.

Fig. 17

X-Ray crystallographic studies reveal that there is no interdinuclear interaction, supporting that the antiferromagnetism is intradinuclear and through σ pathway.

Electrochemical properties of binuclear complexes

In all the binuclear complexes, discussed under magnetic properties, the two metal centres are equivalent with same electronic environment. Hence they should undergo reduction or oxidation at the same potential. Thus the cyclic voltammogram should show one redox peak, corresponding to two-electron reduction. However, there is two-step reduction in cases of several binuclear complexes, each step corresponding to one electron. This supports the conclusion

from the magnetic studies, that there is interaction between the two metal centres.

When there is oxidation or reduction of the metal centre, there is change in the electron density at it. This is communicated to the other metal centre. In case of reduction there is increased electron density at the second metal centre and hence its tendency to get reduced is less and undergoes reduction at a more negative potential. Conversely, in case of oxidation of the first centre, there is reduction in electron density at the other metal centre and it has less tendency to undergo oxidation and gets oxidized at a more positive potential than the first centre.

In the cyclic voltammogram of the binuclear Cu^{II} complexes of the reduced Schiff bases⁹ shown in Fig. 8, there is no reduction peak in the first cathodic cycle. However, the anodic scan shows two-step oxidation. The stepwise oxidation has been shown in Fig. 18.

Fig. 18. Cyclic voltammogram of binuclear Cu^{II} complexes of reduced tridentate Schiff base.

This indicates that there is interaction between the two centres, through the bridging O^- , through σ or π orbitals. A two-step reduction is also observed in the cyclic voltammogram (Fig. 20) of binuclear Cu^{II} complex of the binucleating Schiff base²⁹, shown in Fig. 19, where the two centres are separated by a long bridge with a fractured π -delocalization, due to the presence of the sp^3 hybridized CH_2 group. This supports that the electronic communication between the two metal centres could be through σ -orbital only.

Fig. 19

The stepwise reduction takes place as follows :

Another interesting observation of electron density effect is in Ru^{II} complexes in the binucleating amides derived from the condensation of ethylene-, propylene-, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-phenylenediamine, with pyridine-2-carboxylic acid (Fig.

Fig. 20. Cyclic voltammogram of binuclear Cu^{II} complexes of binucleating Schiff base

21). It is observed that in case of *o*- and *p*-phenylenediamide bridges, there is two-step oxidation, whereas both the centres get oxidized simultaneously in case of the ethylene, propylene and *m*-phenylenediamide bridges³⁰.

Fig. 21

This observation supports the magnetic studies, where it was seen that the π -electronic effects are not significant at *meta*-position and hence there is no interaction between the metal centres in case of *m*-phenylenediamine Schiff base.

The extent of interaction between the two centres is determined by the comproportionation constant K_c which is dependent on the difference in the oxidation or reduction potentials of the two centres,

$$-RT \ln K_c = -nF(\Delta E)$$

where K_c is the equilibrium constant for the reaction,

Greater the ΔE , higher is the K_c , and greater is the probability of the stabilization of the mixed valent complex, like the Creutz Taube ion³¹ (Fig. 22).

Fig. 22

In such mixed valence complexes there is possibility of transferring the electrons from the metal of lower oxidation state to the one in higher oxidation state. Such transitions are called intervalence charge transfer (IVCT), and are evidence of intramolecular electron transfer and provide a vivid support of intermetal interaction. Greater the interac-

tion between the metal centres, lower is the energy of the IVCT band. It has been shown that the energy of the IVCT, and, therefore, the extent of interaction between the metal centres, is dependent on the nature of the bridge³²⁻³⁴.

Such Studies provide models for electron transport in biological systems. In addition, IVCT energy is a measure of the efficiency of the bridging molecule as a conducting wire (molecular wire) for use in molecular size electronic devices.

Homogeneous catalysis

Various metal complexes are being used as homogeneous catalysts to understand the relationship between the nature of the metal ion and the ligand, on the catalytic activity of the complexes. The major goal of this area is to transform the biomimetic catalytic systems to the practical ones.

Various metal complexes have been synthesized to mimic cytochrome P450, a biological mono-oxygenase³⁵. Its effectiveness is attributed to the plane porphyrin ring with extensive π -conjugation and central iron ion with variable valency.

Tetradentate Schiff base complexes³⁶ of transition metal ions, derived from salicylaldehyde, mimic the metalloporphyrin and were found to be more effective for the hydroxylation of alkanes and epoxidation of olefins. However, with N_2O_2 coordination, Schiff base complexes are less effective models for porphyrin complex catalysts. Schiff base complexes derived from pyridine aldehyde with N_4 coordination are better models.

Initial oxygenation studies of hydrocarbon were with molecular oxygen as oxidant. However, since only one oxygen is utilized in this process, the other oxygen has to be reduced, using a reducing agent. This can be avoided by using a mono-oxygen donor oxidant, like iodosylbenzene.

In the catalytic process the metal centre forms an oxo-cation as the intermediate. The oxygen is transferred to the substrate and the metal complex catalyst comes back to the original form (Fig. 23). This is termed oxygen rebound mechanism, as suggested by Groves *et al.*³⁶.

Fig. 23

After transferring oxygen from the metal to the substrate, the metal complex continues the next cycle. Alternatively, formation of a stable μ -oxo species takes place, leading to the termination of the catalytic process. Either pathway depends on the stability of the oxo-cation, which in

turn depends on the electron density around the metal ion in the complex, governed by the nature of the coordinated ligands^{37,38}. If the oxo-cation is very stable, it does not transfer the oxygen to the substrate easily and leads to the formation of the μ -oxo compound and retardation of the catalytic activity. The catalytic activity of the complex can also be retarded due to the oxidative degradation of the ligand part of the complex catalyst.

In biological systems, the metalloenzymes, affecting catalysis are multimetallic systems. Hence binuclear complexes of Schiff bases derived from pyridine aldehyde and *m*- and *p*-phenylenediamines have been used as catalysts for the olefin oxidation reaction and the catalytic activity has been compared with the corresponding mononuclear *o*-phenylenediamine Schiff base complex, using iodosylbenzene as the oxidant^{39, 40} (Fig. 24).

1. M = Mn(II); bridge p-; x = 0
2. M = Mn(II); bridge m-; x = 0
3. M = Fe(III); bridge p-; x = Cl
4. M = Fe(III); bridge m-; x = Cl
5. M = Ru(III); bridge p-; x = Cl
6. M = Ru(III); bridge m-; x = Cl

Fig. 24

The binuclear complexes were found to be better catalysts than the corresponding mononuclear complex, but the yield of the epoxide is less than twice of the mononuclear complexes. This shows that though both the metal centres participate in the catalytic reaction, there may be steric hindrance to the simultaneous approach of the two olefin molecules to the two adjacent metal centres. It was, therefore, thought of interest to investigate the role of the length of the bridging ligand.

Binuclear complexes of Mn^{II} , of ligands with longer bridges, derived from pyridine-2-aldehyde or 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl, 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane or 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl ether (Fig. 25), were synthesized and were used as catalysts⁴¹. It is expected that the increasing length of the bridging ligand should enhance the catalytic activity of the binuclear complex, since the two olefin molecules can be accommodated fully without any steric hindrance, on the two metal centres, which are situated far apart. However, in the present complexes, the catalysts with longer bridges are found to be less catalytic than those with smaller bridges.

Fig. 25

Thus, binuclear complexes do not display the anticipated summed catalytic activity of the two constituent parts because of the communication between the two centres⁴². On oxo-cation formation at one metal centre, there is increase in the positive residual charge on this metal centre. Hence electron density is withdrawn from the other metal centre, and its tendency to form the oxo-cation is inhibited and the catalytic activity of the second centre is reduced.

Thus, the above observation of the catalytic activity also supports the results of the thermodynamic, magnetic and electrochemical studies, that there is an interaction between the two centres in a binuclear complex, separated by long bridges.

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